

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

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1 TABLE OF CONTENTS

2	Abbreviations and Acronyms	5
3	Executive Summary	6
4	Introduction	7
4.1	<i>Procedures and State-of-the-Art</i>	7
4.1.1	Austria	7
4.1.2	Germany	8
4.1.3	Portugal.....	9
4.1.4	Slovakia	9
4.1.5	Spain.....	17
5	Final Notes.....	19
6	Annex I – Site Characterisation Sheets for the Selected Sampling Sites Chosen	20
	Austria.....	21
	Germany	29
	Portugal	40
	Slovakia	47

2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
EMS	Electromagnetic separation
IPB	Iberian Pyrite Belt
TE	Thermoelectric
WP	Work Package
%	Percentage
kg	kilogram
µm	micrometre
mm	millimetre
m ³	cubic metre
wt	weight

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 2.2 of the START project presents a summary of the work being undertaken in WP2 (Selection of mine waste sites; physical minerals separation and concentration) to concentrate the samples of tetrahedrite, aiming to deliver as-pure-as-possible concentrates of this mineral to the other technical WP's in the project to test them and use them in the production of the p-type semiconductor thermoelement.

4 INTRODUCTION

The sampling protocols implemented and adopted by the consortium partners, delivered in D2.1, have ensured that samples were collected in similar manners.

Just as the minerals obtained at each chosen mining site, mineral separation procedures are unique to each site, depending on the challenges the minerals present. This may be due to grain size variations, paragenetic associations and/or intergrowth patterns. Hence, mineral separation procedures vary from site to site to ensure maximum yield for the downstream uses in the project activities.

Below is the state and procedures undertaken by the WP2 consortium partners for mineral concentration.

4.1 PROCEDURES AND STATE-OF-THE-ART

At the outset, even though the mineral separation procedures are not finished for all sites, this has not detracted from the fact mineral concentrates are available and already been sent to consortium partners for implementing the activities planned for WP3 (Materials modelling and processing) related with the production of the p-type semiconductor thermoelement. Therefore, this is not a limiting factor in any way.

4.1.1 Austria

- Samples from 7 different locations were collected: 3 locations in Leogang (Salzburg) and 4 locations in Schwaz (Tyrol) (Table 1; Annex I).
- Hand specimens were collected from 5 of the locations. The remaining 2 points can be described as tailings where sandy material was deposited.
- The total collection was 156 kg of samples, which apparently contained fahlore.
- The raw samples were crushed at the Montanuniversität Leoben (Chair of Mineral Processing). After that, the samples were separated on sieves into the following fractions:
 - < 315 μm
 - 315 – 1000 μm
 - > 1 mm
- An attempt was made to separate the rocks based on the differences in density. Therefore, a gravity separator (shaking table) was used. However, due to the similar mineral densities, this method was not successful.
- Mineral separation is under way.

Table 1: Details of the sampling campaign undertaken in the Austrian sites.

Location	Sampling point name	Type	X_3035	Y_3035	Coordinate system	EPSG	Z-coordinate	Sampling Date
Leogang	Nöckelberg Halde	Waste mine dump	4523264.98	2705747.89	ETRS89	4258	1306	29.- 30/08/2022
	Barbarastollen - Bereich Gipsschacht	Abandoned mine shaft	4522849.07	2704632.27	ETRS89	4258	1050	30/08/2022
	Barbarastollen - Maria Heimsuchung	Abandoned mine shaft	4522920.95	2704644.48	ETRS89	4258	1067	31/08/2022
Schwaz	Sandpocher Haldentop Nord	Tailings	4452038.11	2694685.81	ETRS89	4258	639	01/09/2022
	Sandpocher Haldentop Süd	Tailings	4452058.04	2694702.91	ETRS89	4258	641	01/09/2022
	Antonihalde	Waste mine dump	4452462.21	2694713.12	ETRS89	4258	730	01/09/2022
	Sigmundhalde	Waste mine dump	4453347.91	2694663.02	ETRS89	4258	1088	02/09/2022

4.1.2 Germany

A sulphide-rich concentrate from a large tailings site, previously collected and processed by means of flotation in the REMINTA Project – TU Clausthal, was kindly made available for use in START. This is a sulphide-concentrate from the “Bollrich Teiche” (Goslar, Rammelsberg). This sample contains 49 wt. % pyrite, 3 wt. % sphalerite, 4 wt. % galena, very minor contents of fahlore/tetrahedrite, and different gangue minerals (Annex 1).

These minerals (pyrite, galena, sphalerite, and to a lesser extent chalcopyrite), are usually the most abundant sulphide-containing minerals at larger German mine waste sites. To our current knowledge, tetrahedrite has been reported to occur as a subordinate mineral only.

Following the promising results from the other partners with historical mining sites, new sampling campaigns on small historic mine waste dumps in the Black Forest area are underway, targeting residues from the mining of veins rich in fahlore, copper-, and/or antimony minerals (Annex I). The collected samples are currently being analysed and, if possible, will be processed to obtain concentrates for further use in START.

Additionally, fahlore-rich concentrates from German primary ores are made available for use in START, to offer a possibility to test different types of natural tetrahedrites for their use in TE devices.

4.1.3 Portugal

The massive Corvo sulphide deposit, located in Neves-Corvo mine is characterized by the presence of complex sulphide ore with high As and Cu content. These sulphides contain intermittent pockets consisting of tennantite-tetrahedrite ore. Since the ore was previously tested in mineralogical and high energy milling conditions, it is suitable to be used for START testing purposes (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A to D: Inspection, stope face, marking and drilling for blasting stope face; E – collected ore and, F – photomicrograph of Corvo Ore (Green arrow = chalcopyrite; Red arrows = tetrahedrite-tennantite; Yellow arrows: pyrite).

Despite the access to the mine underground works being limited and intermittent, a total of 700 kg of sample were still collected. From these, detailed petrographic studies were undertaken in three polished sections. Samples were delivered to WP3 partners.

4.1.4 Slovakia

Three tetrahedrite samples were collected from Rožňava (6th level of Silver vein), ready after electromagnetic separation (EMS) (Figure 2):

- 11-tetrahedrite concentrate after the 2nd EMS at 6 A from the fraction 0.355 – 0.5 mm
- 12-tetrahedrite concentrate after the 2nd EMS at 12 A from the fraction 0.2 – 0.355 mm
- 13-tetrahedrite concentrate after the 2nd EMS at 12 A from the fraction 0.1 – 0.2 mm

Figure 2: The different size fractions collected at the Rožňava Mine (Annex I).

The processing of the raw tetrahedrite sample from the Rožňava Mine was done according to the following methodology:

- The raw sample of tetrahedrite from the Rožňava (Slovakia) of approximately 88 kg was delivered to the laboratories of Department of Applied Technology of Raw Materials on November 21, 2022. The sample was crushed (I °), homogenized and quartered.
- After that, the sample was crushed (II °, III °) and separated by sieving (according to Figure 3). The fraction over 1.0 mm was grinded in the mill and again sorted on sieves.
- The fractions up to 0.1 mm were processed by EMS - dry way - at different intensities of saturating electric current, while the fraction below 0.1 mm was processed by flotation (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Processing of the raw tetrahedrite sample; EMS – electromagnetic separation, MP – magnetic product, NP – non-magnetic product, ○ - sample name/number.

The inputs and products were characterized by X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD). using a diffractometer D2 Phaser (Bruker, Germany), equipped with a $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation source (30 kV, 10 mA) and LynxEye detector. The data were qualitatively and quantitatively analysed using Software DIFFRAC.EVA with PDF-2 Database.

Results

The major mineral phases in the raw tetrahedrite sample were siderite and tetrahedrite (Figure 4). After the crushing and sorting on sieves, no significant changes in the mineralogy were observed in the samples of granularity over 0.5 mm (Figures 5 and 6). For the fractions below 0.5 mm, the concentration of tetrahedrite slightly increased with decreasing granularity (Figures 6 to 9). The highest content of tetrahedrite was detected in the finest sample (Figure 10). Based on XRD analysis, it can be concluded that samples of granularity below 0.5 mm contained concentrates with higher amount of tetrahedrite. These samples, denoted 11, 12, 13 (Figure 2) are the focus of this report.

Figure 4: XRD analysis of raw tetrahedrite sample.

Figure 5: XRD analysis of raw tetrahedrite sample of granularity 0.71 – 1.0 mm.

Figure 6: XRD analysis of raw tetrahedrite sample of granularity 0.5 – 0.71 mm.

Figure 7: XRD analysis of raw tetrahedrite sample of granularity 0.355 – 0.5 mm.

Figure 8: XRD analysis of raw tetrahedrite sample of granularity 0.2 – 0.355 mm.

Figure 9: XRD analysis of raw tetrahedrite sample of granularity 0.1 – 0.2 mm.

Figure 10: XRD analysis of raw tetrahedrite sample of granularity below 0.1 mm.

The samples with grain size > 0.355 mm were electromagnetically separated in two steps, first at intensity of saturating electric current 1 A, then at 6 A. The samples below 0.355 mm were separated at 1 A and then at 12 A. The products after the second EMS were characterized by XRD analysis. In each product, an increase in tetrahedrite concentration was observed, with small content of accessory minerals (Figures 11 to 15). The highest amount of accessory minerals after the EMS were observed in the most coarse-grained sample (Figure 10). Except for the fraction 0.355 - 0.5 mm (Figure 13) the samples still contained a small amount of siderite.

Figure 11: XRD pattern of magnetic product after electromagnetic separation of fraction 0.71 – 0.1 mm at 6 A.

Figure 12: XRD pattern of magnetic product after electromagnetic separation of fraction 0.5 – 0.71 mm at 6 A.

Figure 13: XRD pattern of magnetic product after electromagnetic separation of fraction 0.355 – 0.5 mm at 6 A.

Figure 14: XRD pattern of magnetic product after electromagnetic separation of fraction 0.2 – 0.355 mm at 12 A.

Figure 15: XRD pattern of magnetic product after electromagnetic separation of fraction 0.1 – 0.2 mm at 12 A.

The sludge EMS (wet way) of the finest fraction was also tested, but the formation of a thin greasy layer was observed to prevent the separation process in the separation cell.

Moreover, the flotation of the finest fraction was tested. The flotation is a demanding, time-consuming process, requiring testing of various reagents and optimization. Experiments are still underway and will continue during the following months.

The input samples (fractions) and products after the EMS were sent to the Geoanalytical laboratories of State Geological Institute for chemical analysis. According to the initial processing and results, the samples of larger granularity should be first grinded, then separated by EMS at higher intensity of electric current or processed by flotation.

To date a total of 4 kg of concentrates have been sent to the partners of Task 3.2 (Mechanochemical synthesis of mineral-derived sulphide p-type materials).

4.1.5 Spain

In Spain, 21 sites were selected, *a priori*, with high potential in tetrahedrite from IGME's Mineral Resources database (Table 2). Following the criteria such as % tetrahedrite, grain size and the volume of mine waste, this number was reduced.

Table 2: Mine waste sites with high potential in tetrahedrite from IGME's Mineral Resources database.

Sites	Volume mine waste	% tetrahedrite	Grain size	Evaluation
SUDPortuguesa Zone				
La Sierrecilla (Infanta)	3.500 m ³	abundant	mm - μm	suitable
Romanera	10.000 m ³	scarce	mm - μm	rejected
Tharsis	3-5. 10 T	medium	mm - μm	under consideration
Asturiano-Leonesa Zone				
Segunda Cobriza	6.000 m ³	scarce	--	rejected
Peña Negra	500 m ³	abundant	mm	suitable
Cantabrica Zone				
Mina Delfina	6.000 m ³	scarce	--	rejected
Ninón	100 m ³	scarce	--	rejected
Llucias	250 m ³	scarce	--	rejected
Coriellu	500 m ³	presence	mm	suitable
Iberian Cordillera				
Serrana	2.000 m ³	unknown	unknown	under consideration
Alpartir	10.000 m ³	unknown	unknown	under consideration
Hombrados	200 m ³	scarce	--	under consideration
Torres de Albarracín	6.000 m ³ + 3.000 m ³	abundant	mm	suitable
Collado de la Plata	8.000 m ³	scarce	--	rejected
Santa Filomena	8.000 m ³	unknown	mm	under consideration
Central Sistem				
Hiendelancina	15.000 m ³	scarce	--	rejected
Betic Cordillera				
Lanteira	50.000 m ³	abundant	mm	suitable
Ossa Morena Zone				
Guadalcanal	50.000 m ³	unknown	unknown	under consideration
La Nava	100.000 m ³	unknown	unknown	under consideration
Pyrenees				
Os de Civis	2.000 m ³	unknown	unknown	under consideration
Rocabruna	200 m ³	unknown	unknown	under consideration

- SUDPortuguesa (South Portuguese) Zone: from La Sierrecilla mine in IPB, approximately 30 Kg of all/one were collected. All samples were milled but the tetrahedrites have not been separated yet. Due to a much smaller grain size than expected, delays are taking place in the mineralogical separation phase. Paragenesis and grain size have been studied. Tharsis, has the same problem regarding the grain size, but the huge volume of mine waste allows us to reconsider it as a good place for sampling.
- Cantabrica Zone: Coriellu was eventually selected but with certain limitations due to both the limited % of tetrahedrite and the volume of the dump.
- Iberian Cordillera: a series of mines in the Iberian Cordillera (centre of Spain) were visited. Here small vein Cu deposits were found, where the tetrahedrite was the main Cu source. In the Torres de Albarracín mine, a good amount of tetrahedrite samples was collected. These are accompanied by siderite, which has a larger grain size. These should separate quite well, in an experimental way.
- Betic Cordillera: by the moment the mining waste was sampled, the % of tetrahedrite and the size observed allow us to consider this place with high potential.

There are additional samples in the laboratory undergoing mineral separation to deliver to the consortium partners of WP3.

5 FINAL NOTES

- Samples from different sites are at different stages of production/concentration.
- Methodologies for sampling are distinct for every ore sample, depending on the paragenesis.
- Each partner in WP2 is separating the ore samples, to obtain samples with the highest possible amount of tetrahedrite/tennantite.
- Samples have already percolated to WP3 to be used as raw materials in the production of the p-type semiconductor thermoelements.

6 ANNEX I – SITE CHARACTERISATION SHEETS FOR THE SELECTED SAMPLING SITES CHOSEN

AUSTRIA

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET		Date: 01.09.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATANTO006		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4452462.21 Y: 2694713.11	
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeiderer, R. Strauss			
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher			
Mine name		Schwaz – Mining district Falkenstein			
Deposit type		Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite			
Mine Status		<input type="checkbox"/> Working Mine		<input type="checkbox"/> Abandoned Mine	
Sample type		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Spotted		<input type="checkbox"/> Well	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Simple		<input type="checkbox"/> Composite		<input type="checkbox"/> Channel	
STATE		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Oxidised		<input type="checkbox"/> Fresh	
Mine waste type		<input type="checkbox"/> Waste rock		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Waste rock dump	
		<input type="checkbox"/> Tailings		<input type="checkbox"/> Stockpiles	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 12.000 Square meters			
Material size		<input type="checkbox"/> Sand		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gravel	
		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stones	
Mineralogy		Fahlore, Nickelskutterudite, Malachite, Chalcopryrite, Stibnite, Azurite, Mercury, Devilline, Chalcostibite, Spangolite, Covellite, Realgar, Cinnabar, Tyrolite			
Photos					
Comments		Figure 1: ATANTO006			

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: 30.08.2022 Country: Austria			
Sample ID: ATGISH003		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4522849.07	Y: 2704632.26				
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeleiderer, T. Unterweissacher, R. Strauss							
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher							
Mine name		Barbarastollen Gipsschacht							
Deposit type		Polymetallic Cu-Ni-Co-Hg-Ag							
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X			
Sample type		Spotted		X	Well		Channel		
Simple		Composite		X	Number of sub samples				
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh			
Mine waste type		Waste rock		x		Waste rock dump			
		Tailings				Stockpiles			
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Samples from inside the mine. Dimension cannot be estimated.							
Material size		Sand		Gravel		x	Stones		x
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals include tennantite, chalcopyrite, cinnabar, galena, bornite and magnesite							
Photos		<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 2: ATGISH003</p>							
Comments									

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET		Date: 31.08.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATMAHE002		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4522920.95	Y: 2704644.47
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeleiderer, T. Unterweissacher, R. Strauss			
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher			
Mine name		Barbarastollen Maria Heimsuchung			
Deposit type		Polymetallic Cu-Ni-Co-Hg-Ag			
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine	
Sample type		Spotted		Channel	
Simple		X		Well	
Composite		X		Number of sub samples	
STATE		Oxidised		Fresh	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump	
		Tailings		Stockpiles	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Samples from inside the mine. Dimension cannot be estimated.			
Material size		Sand		Stones	
		Gravel		x	
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals include tennantite, chalcopryrite, cinnabar, galena, bornite and magnesite			
Photos					
Comments		Figure 3: ATMAHE002			

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 30.08.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATNOEK001		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)	X: 4523264.98		Y: 2705747.89	
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeiderer, R. Strauss, T. Unterweissacher				
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher				
Mine name		Leogang-Noeckelberg				
Deposit type		Polymetallic Cu-Ni-Co-Hg-Ag				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well	Channel	
Simple	Composite	X	Number of sub samples			
STATE		Oxidised		X	Fresh	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		X
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 6.000 Square meters (ca. 160x110m)				
Material size		Sand		Gravel	x	Stones
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals include tennantite, chalcopryrite, cinnabar, galena, bornite and magnesite				
Photos		<p>Figure 4: ATNOEK001</p>				
Comments						

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 01.09.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATSAPO004		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4452038.11		Y: 2694685.81
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeiderer, R. Strauss				
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher				
Mine name		Schwaz – Mining district Falkenstein				
Deposit type		Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X
Sample type		Spotted		Well		Channel
Simple		Composite		Number of sub samples		
STATE		Oxidised		Fresh		
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 49.000 Square meters				
Material size		Sand		Gravel		Stones
Mineralogy						
Photos		<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 5: ATSAPO004</p>				
Comments						

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 01.09.2022 Country: Austria				
Sample ID: ATSAPO005		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4452058.04		Y: 2694702.90			
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeleiderer, R. Strauss							
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher							
Mine name		Schwaz – Mining district Falkenstein							
Deposit type		Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite							
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X			
Sample type		Spotted		X	Well		Channel		
Simple		Composite		X		Number of sub samples			
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh			
Mine waste type		Waste rock			Waste rock dump				
		Tailings			x		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 49.000 Square meters							
Material size		Sand		x		Gravel		Stones	
Mineralogy									
Photos		<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 6: ATSAPO005</p>							
Comments									

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 02.09.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATSIGM007		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)	X: 4453347.91		Y: 2694663.02	
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeiderer				
Organization		Geosphere Austria				
Mine name		Schwaz – Mining district Falkenstein				
Deposit type		Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well		Channel
Simple		Composite	X	Number of sub samples		
STATE		Oxidised	X		Fresh	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		X
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 49.000 Square meters				
Material size		Sand		Gravel	x	Stones
Mineralogy		Fahlore, Nickelskutterudite, Malachite, Chalcopyrite, Stibnite, Azurite, Mercury, Devilline, Chalcostibite, Spangolite, Covellite, Realgar, Cinnabar, Tyrolite				
Photos						
Comments						

Figure 7: ATSIGM007

GERMANY

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 2015 Country: Germany	
Sample ID: GER/BT/001/RSCP5_1		Coordinates: (ETRS89) X: 10.464828		Y: 51.902923		
Sampler		REWITA project consortium				
Organization		CUTEC, PPM, HMG, STÖBICH, PDV, BIG, TUC				
Mine name		Rammelsberg mine (Harz Mountains, Germany)				
Deposit type		SEDEX type deposit (black smoker) of Devonian age, folded and compressed during development of the Harz.				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine	since 1988	
Sample type		Spotted		Well	x	Channel
Simple		Composite	x	Number of sub samples		1 (sulphide concentrate)
STATE		Oxidised		Fresh		x
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		
		Tailings		x	Stockpiles	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Square meters: 600,000 m ² (approx. 7 Mio. t)				
Material size		Sand	X (silt-clay)	Gravel		Stones
Mineralogy		<p>Average tailings composition: 55% carbonates and silicates, 25% barite, and 20% sulphides (Römer and Goldmann, 2019).</p> <p>The tailings (Fig. 4) were sampled, analysed, and processed by the REWITA project consortium. More information on this project can be found in the comments below. A subsample of a sulphide concentrate was kindly made available for START (sample ID GER/BT/001/RSCP5_1). The subsample had been stored at low temperatures and under water to prevent oxidation. At BGR, the sample was freeze-dried (Fig. 5) and was analyzed with XRD (Fig. 1), optical microscopy (Fig. 2), and SEM-MLA (Fig. 3).</p>				

Fig. 1: XRD spectrum of sample GER/BT/001/RSCP5_1

XRD analysis of the concentrate subsample reveals that the modal mineralogy consists mainly of pyrite (49 wt%), barite (10 wt%), muscovite (9 wt%), chlorite (5 wt%), galena (4 wt%), sphalerite (3 wt%), carbonate (10 wt%), feldspars (4 %), and quartz (4%). The common accessory minerals are chalcoppyrite, gypsum and pyrrhotite. Tetrahedrites were not detected with XRD.

The pyrite crystals are mostly extremely fine grained (< 30 μm). Its crystal shape varies from euhedral to anhedral and it occurs as single crystals along the sample matrix (see Fig. 3 & 4). Sphalerite and galena show even finer-grained crystals when compared to pyrite and the crystal shapes tend to be anhedral as shown in the Fig 3 and 4.

Fig. 2: Photomicrographs of sample GER/BT/001/RSCP5_1. Minerals: ccp – chalcoppyrite, gn – galena and py – pyrite.

	<table border="0" data-bbox="667 667 1361 846"> <tr> <td>■ Rutile</td> <td>■ Apatite</td> <td>■ Orthoclase</td> <td>■ Biotite</td> </tr> <tr> <td>■ Gypsum</td> <td>■ Bournonite</td> <td>■ Albite</td> <td>■ Fe-Oxihydroxides</td> </tr> <tr> <td>■ Dolomite</td> <td>■ Calcite</td> <td>■ Pyrrhotite</td> <td>■ Siderite</td> </tr> <tr> <td>■ Chalcopyrite</td> <td>■ Pb-Mn-Fe-(S,Zn)</td> <td>■ Chlorite</td> <td>■ Ankerite</td> </tr> <tr> <td>■ Galena</td> <td>■ Muscovite</td> <td>■ Quartz</td> <td>■ Sphalerite</td> </tr> <tr> <td>■ Barite</td> <td>■ Pyrite</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table> <p data-bbox="608 862 1141 896">Fig. 3: GXMAP of sample GER/BT/001/RSCP5_1</p>	■ Rutile	■ Apatite	■ Orthoclase	■ Biotite	■ Gypsum	■ Bournonite	■ Albite	■ Fe-Oxihydroxides	■ Dolomite	■ Calcite	■ Pyrrhotite	■ Siderite	■ Chalcopyrite	■ Pb-Mn-Fe-(S,Zn)	■ Chlorite	■ Ankerite	■ Galena	■ Muscovite	■ Quartz	■ Sphalerite	■ Barite	■ Pyrite		
■ Rutile	■ Apatite	■ Orthoclase	■ Biotite																						
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■ Galena	■ Muscovite	■ Quartz	■ Sphalerite																						
■ Barite	■ Pyrite																								
<p data-bbox="228 1272 316 1305">Photos</p>	<p data-bbox="608 1563 1177 1597">Fig. 5: Sample GER/BT/001/RSCP5_1 (freeze-dried)</p>																								
<p data-bbox="228 1816 359 1850">Comments</p>	<p data-bbox="608 1653 1361 1977">A recent research project (REWITA) funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) investigated the presence of Cu, Co, Zn, Ag, Ga, In, and other valuable metals in minerals (barite, sulfides, silicate, etc.) in the Rammelsberg Bollriche tailings pond in detail (Schirmer et al., 2017). Thereto, drill cores from different depths and locations were collected by the REWITA project consortium. A process scheme for the recovery and complete reprocessing of the Bollrich tailings material has been developed and tested at laboratory scale (Römer et al., 2018; Römer and Goldmann, 2019).</p>																								

	<p>For more information on the Rammelsberg Bollriche Tailings pond can be found in:</p> <p>Goldmann, Remining of the historical Rammelsberg tailing ponds, Germany, Symposium (Re)Mining extractive waste, a new business?, Mechelen 2022; https://re-mine.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/0_1_Goldmann-ReMining-2022-Mechelen-1.pdf</p> <p>F. Römer, D. Goldmann, Wiederaufbereitung eines bergbaulichen Abfalls im Harz – Wie aus Altlasten in Zukunft vielleicht Lagerstätten werden., CHEMKON 2019, 26, 66. DOI: 10.1002/ckon.201800080</p> <p>Römer, F., Binder, A., & Goldmann, D. (2018). Basic considerations for the reprocessing of sulfidic tailings using the example of the bollrich tailing ponds. World of Metallurgy - ERZMETALL, 71(3), 135-143. Retrieved from www.scopus.com</p> <p>Schirmer, T., Römer, F., Elwert, T., Goldmann, D., Characterization of tailings of the Rammelsberg ore deposit for a potential reprocessing. Proceedings of the 9th European Metallurgical conference, EMC 2017, 25-28 June 2017, www.scopus.com</p> <p>Project REWITA (funded by BMBF, 2015-2018): https://www.rewimet.de/aktivitaeten/projekte/rewita</p> <p>Project REMINTA (funded by BMBF, 2020–2023): https://www.reminta.de/</p>
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		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 2013-2014 Country: Germany		
Sample ID: GER/BW/001/xxx		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 10.284092	Y: 51.80572		
Sampler		Kerstin Kuhn and Jeannette Meima					
Organization		Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR)					
Mine name		Bergwerkswohlfahrt mine (Harz Mountains, Germany)					
Deposit type		Lead- and silver-rich hydrothermal veins from the eastern part of the "Silbernaaler" vein system.					
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine	since 1950s		
Sample type		Spotted		Well	x	Channel	x
Simple	Composite	Number of sub samples			8 sub samples (collected from 7 drill holes, 1 excavation)		
STATE		Oxidised	x	Fresh	x		
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump	x		
		Tailings		Stockpiles			
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Square meters: 15,000 m ² (approx. 82,000 m ³)					
Material size		Sand	x	Gravel	x	Stones	
Mineralogy		<p>The Bergwerkswohlfahrt mine waste dump (Fig. 3) is very heterogeneous. It consists of large areas with stamp mill tailings alternating with areas consisting of blocky material (Kuhn and Meima, 2019). The dump was sampled by BGR by taking drill cores (Fig. 4) as part of the ROBEHA project (for more information, see comments below). The remaining dry-stored ROBEHA drill cores from holes "F", "G", "I", "J", "L", "O", "S" (Kuhn and Meima, 2019) as well as residues from an excavation ("S"), have been made available for START.</p> <p>In START, the stamp mill residues were collected from the drill cores and excavation residues, yielding 8 subsamples and about 55 kg of sample material in total. This material is now being processed to separate the sulphide minerals from the wall rock minerals.</p>					

	<p>Fig. 2: BSE and MLA images of bulk sample GER/BW/001/S1-30a<1mm_2/52437 showing accessory tetrahedrite (ttr - blue) grains.</p> <p>The mineralogy of the stamp mill residues from the excavation „S“ (grain size fraction < 1 mm; sample ID GER/BW/001/S1-30a<1mm_2/52437) has been investigated in detail using microscopy (Fig. 1), SEM-MLA (Fig. 2), and microprobe (Appendix 1) analysis. Its modal mineralogy shows a broad variety of minerals. The sulphide content generally increases with decreasing grain size. The most common sulphide is galena (3 – 12 wt%, depending on the grain size range). There are also other sulphide occurrences, such as sphalerite, tetrahedrite, chalcopyrite, and pyrite, however, these sulphides occur as accessory minerals. Common gangue minerals include quartz (53 wt%), barite (6 wt%), carbonate (11 wt%), muscovite (15 wt%) and gypsum (1 wt%). The sulphides are mostly associated with quartz and carbonates (see Fig. 1 and 2); however, the finer-grained crystals tend to be fully liberated in the samples. The chemical composition of the tetrahedrite crystals based on electron microprobe analysis is shown in Table 1 in the appendix.</p>
<p>Photos</p>	<p>Kuhn & Meima, 2019</p> <p>Fig. 3: Photo of the Bergwerkswohlfahrt mining waste rock dump</p>

	<p>100 cm</p> <p>Fig. 4: Drill cores GER/BW/002/A (drill hole A)</p>
<p>Comments</p>	<p>A former research project (ROBEHA) funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) investigated the Bergwerkswohlfahrt mine waste sites and others in the West-Harz. Drill cores from different depths and locations were collected from the Bergwerkswohlfahrt mine dump and analysed with Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy by BGR as described in Kuhn and Meima (2019). These mining residues were found to contain significant amounts of sulphide minerals, including galena, sphalerite, as well as accessory chalcocopyrite and tetrahedrite.</p> <p>More information on the Bergwerkswohlfahrt dump: Kuhn, K., Meima, J.A., 2019. Characterization and Economic Potential of Historic Tailings from Gravity Separation: Implications from a Mine Waste Dump (Pb-Ag) in the Harz Mountains Mining District, Germany. Minerals 9, 303. https://doi.org/10.3390/min9050303</p> <p>The ROBEHA project (funded by BMBF, 2012-2015): https://www.robeha.de/ROBEHA/DE/Home/robeha_node.html</p>

Table 1: Tetrahedrite chemical composition based on electron microprobe analysis of sample GER/BW/001/S1-30a<1mm_2/52437.

Tetrahedrite	wt%																	
SAMPLE	S	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	As	Ag	Cd	In	Sn	Sb	Hg	Pb	Bi	TOTAL
2301842 Korn1_001	24,933	0,000	1,418	0,000	0,000	21,120	5,208	0,000	0,098	19,442	0,037	0,000	0,000	25,680	0,117	0,000	0,000	98,051
2301842 Korn1_002	23,648	0,000	1,266	0,000	0,000	17,472	4,943	0,000	0,097	23,961	0,000	0,000	0,000	26,463	0,000	0,000	0,044	97,895
2301842 Korn2_003	23,837	0,000	1,592	0,000	0,000	25,676	5,617	0,000	0,139	15,176	0,027	0,000	0,018	28,122	0,000	0,000	0,033	100,237
2301842 Korn2_004	22,791	0,000	1,732	0,000	0,000	23,321	5,207	0,000	0,086	18,199	0,038	0,000	0,061	28,661	0,000	0,000	0,055	100,152
2301842 Korn2_005	22,682	0,000	1,766	0,000	0,000	22,758	5,294	0,000	0,122	16,485	0,051	0,000	0,021	28,075	0,000	0,000	0,048	97,302
2301842 Korn2_006	23,685	0,000	1,832	0,000	0,000	24,597	5,307	0,000	0,090	15,806	0,043	0,000	0,011	27,902	0,000	0,025	0,033	99,330
2301842 Korn3_007	23,120	0,000	1,754	0,000	0,000	19,557	5,062	0,000	1,202	22,548	0,016	0,000	0,029	26,031	0,000	0,000	0,041	99,360
2301842 Korn3_008	23,379	0,000	1,899	0,000	0,000	19,339	6,069	0,000	1,042	19,990	0,000	0,000	0,000	25,368	0,103	0,000	0,062	97,251
2301842 Korn4_012	20,202	0,000	2,430	0,008	0,010	15,715	3,925	0,040	0,000	21,659	0,025	0,000	0,000	25,926	0,000	7,473	0,000	97,415
2301842 Korn5_013	23,165	0,013	1,216	0,000	0,000	22,657	5,895	0,000	0,068	19,022	0,000	0,000	0,041	27,866	0,000	0,000	0,046	99,988
2301842 Korn5_014	22,874	0,011	0,980	0,000	0,000	23,105	6,250	0,000	0,042	17,008	0,000	0,000	0,000	27,957	0,000	0,000	0,035	98,263

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 12.09.2023	
Sample ID: GER/SS-Wi/003		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 8.341387	Y: 48.336595	
Sampler		J. Meima				
Organization		BGR				
Mine name		Schmiedestollen, Frisch Glück-, and St. Joseph mine (probably)				
Deposit type		Barite-fluorite veins with Ag-Co-Bi-U minerals in granite; Ag-bearing quartz veins with Cu, Sb, Zn, Pb minerals.				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine	x	
Sample type		Spotted	x	Well		Channel
Simple		Composite	x	Number of sub samples		
STATE		Oxidised	x	Fresh		
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump	x	
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 0.3 ha and 10000 m ³				
Material size		Sand	x	Gravel	x	Stones
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals: high variety of minerals containing Cu, Sb, Zn, Pb, Bi, U, Ag, Co; e.g. fahlore.				
Photos						
Comments		Under evaluation. Mineral collecting locality. Because of its very complex mineralogy probably not ideal for use in START.				

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: 15.09.2023	
						Country: Germany	
Sample ID: GER/SB-Ge/004		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 8.084279		Y: 48. 437308	
Sampler		J. Meima					
Organization		BGR					
Mine name		Silberbrünnle mine					
Deposit type		Quartz veins with Cu and Pb minerals in gneiss; chert debris with Pb minerals.					
Mine Status		Working Mine		<input type="checkbox"/>		Abandoned Mine	
Mine Status		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Sample type		Spotted		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Well	
Sample type		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		Channel	
Simple		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Number of sub samples		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Simple		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Composite		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
STATE		Oxidised		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Fresh	
STATE		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		<input type="checkbox"/>		Waste rock dump	
Mine waste type		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Mine waste type		Tailings		<input type="checkbox"/>		Stockpiles	
Mine waste type		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 0.35 ha and 4000 m ³					
Material size		Sand		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Gravel	
Material size		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		Stones	
Material size		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals: different Cu and Pb minerals including remnant sulphide minerals and various weathered phases.					
Photos							
Comments		Under evaluation. Mineral collecting locality. Because of extensive weathering probably not ideal for use in Start.					

PORTUGAL

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET		Date: 15/11/2022 Country: Portugal	
Sample ID: PT/BRAN/001/A		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 11148.71	Y: -234497.867
Sampler		Igor Morais and Luís Albardeiro			
Organization		LNEG – Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia			
Mine name		Brancanes mine			
Deposit type		Veins – Quartz vein N40°E; 80SE			
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine	
				X	
Sample type		Spotted		Channel	
		X			
Simple		Composite		Number of sub samples	
X					
STATE		Oxidized		Fresh	
		X			
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump	
				X	
		Tailings		Stockpiles	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Small			
Material size		Sand		Stones	
				X	
Mineralogy		Quartz, chalcopyrite, pyrite, carbonates, azurite, covellite			
Photos					

<p>Comments</p>	

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET		Date: 15/11/2022 Country: Portugal	
Sample ID: PT/BARR/001/A		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 18753.299	Y: -238839.436
Sampler		Igor Morais and Luís Albardeiro			
Organization		LNEG – Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia			
Mine name		Barrigão mine			
Deposit type		Veins – two systems of quartz veins associated with struck slips			
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine	X
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well	Channel
Simple	X	Composite	Number of sub samples		
STATE		Oxidized	X	Fresh	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump	X
		Tailings		Stockpiles	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Medium			
Material size		Sand		Gravel	Stones X
Mineralogy		chalcopyrite, tennantite, tetrahedrite, and pyrite, with minor or rare arsenopyrite, löllingite, sphalerite, native bismuth, and an undetermined Cu–Sn–Ge-sulphide; quartz and carbonates (Reiser et al., 2010)			
Photos					

<p>Comments</p>	<p>The ore samples revealed anomalous Sn and Ge contents with an average of 320 and 61 ppm, respectively, ranging between 16 and 872 ppm for Sn and 4 and 280 ppm for Ge.</p>

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 15/09/2022	
Sample ID: PT/NC/001/A		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 14581.949	Y: -232446.128	
Sampler		Igor Morais and Luís Albardeiro				
Organization		LNEG – Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia				
Mine name		Neves-Corvo mine				
Deposit type		VMS – 7 ore bodies with high grades of Cu and Zn				
Mine Status		Working Mine	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandoned Mine		
Sample type		Spotted	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Well	Channel	
Simple	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Composite	Number of sub samples			
STATE		Oxidized		Fresh	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste						
Material size		Sand		Gravel	Stones	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Mineralogy		Chalcopyrite, pyrite, tetrahedrite, quartz, jarosite, sulphur, melanterite, sphalerite, stannite				
Photos						

<p>Comments</p>	<p>Because the access to the mine underground works is limited and intermittent, a total of 700 kg of sample were collected.</p>

SLOVAKIA

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 16/11/2022 Country: Slovakia	
Sample ID: SK/RV/001/A		Coordinates: (ETRS89-TM34 (E, N))	X: 466221 m		Y: 5391602 m	
Sampler		Kubač, Kúšik				
Organization		ŠGÚDŠ				
Mine name		Mária mine				
Deposit type		Early Paleozoic metasedimentary/metavolcanitic				
Mine Status		Working Mine	X	Abandoned Mine		
Sample type		Spotted		Well		Channel
Simple	X	Composite		Number of sub samples		5
STATE		Oxidised		Fresh		X
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Square meters				
Material size		Sand		Gravel		Stones X
Mineralogy		Siderite and quartz–sulphide mineralization: The most abundant ore minerals are tetrahedrite, chalcopyrite, pyrite and arsenopyrite. Brittle, steel-grey coloured tetrahedrite, which is the most important ore mineral, is spatially controlled by the older siderite that is in the form of reticulated veins and clusters. A more brittle tetrahedrite variety with steel blue colour and high metallic lustre is usually enriched by Cu, Ag, Bi, Sb and Hg. A darker low lustre variety contains more Zn and Fe.				
Photos		Photos organized by sample ID. Ex: SK/RV-001/01; SK/RV-001/02; SK/RV-001/03; SK/RV-001/04; SK/RV-001/05; SK/RV-001/06; SK/RV-001/07; SK/RV-001/08; SK/RV-001/09; SK/RV-001/10; SK/RV-001/11; SK/RV-001/12; SK/RV-001/13;				
Comments						